

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Response of different rice varieties to *Azospirillum* sp. inoculation

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We raised TKM9, ADT36, IR50, and ADT37 during Jul-Oct 1987. Soil was

fertilized with 75 kg N/ha in the form of urea in 3 splits (50%, 25%, 25%), 37.5 kg P/ha in the form of superphosphate (all basal), and 37.5 kg K/ha in the form of muriate of potash (all basal).

Bacterial inoculation was done by soaking 60 kg seeds for 24 h in 60 liters water containing 2 kg peat-based inoculum. Sprouted seeds were sown in the nursery. At 25 d after seeding,

seedlings were pulled up and the roots dipped for 20 min in 40 liters water containing 2 kg inoculum. Another 2 kg inoculum was mixed with 15 kg sand and broadcast in the main field before transplanting. Plot size was 15 m² with 3 replications.

Azospirillum sp. inoculation increased number of productive tillers and straw and grain yield of all test varieties (see table). □

Response of rice varieties to *Azospirillum* inoculation. TRRI, Aduthurai, India, 1987.

Variety	Productive tillers (no./hill)			Straw yield (t/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Without <i>Azospirillum</i>	With <i>Azospirillum</i>	Increase (%)	Without <i>Azospirillum</i>	With <i>Azospirillum</i>	Increase (%)	Without <i>Azospirillum</i>	With <i>Azospirillum</i>	Increase (%)
TKM9	7.1 ± 0.3	8.1 ± 0.7	14	5.4 ± 1.0	6.9 ± 1.3	27	4.4 ± 0.7	5.4 ± 0.9	22
ADT36	6.0 ± 0.4	7.1 ± 0.7	18	4.7 ± 0.2	5.9 ± 0.5	26	4.0 ± 0.1	5.0 ± 0.2	26
IR50	7.2 ± 0.3	8.4 ± 0.3	17	4.2 ± 0.3	5.7 ± 0.7	35	3.6 ± 0.5	5.0 ± 0.4	38
ADT37	5.3 ± 0.5	6.6 ± 0.6	24	4.6 ± 0.3	5.8 ± 0.2	27	3.9 ± 0.2	4.8 ± 0.2	24

Green manure crop performance in semiarid region of India

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A field trial during 1986-1987 wet and dry seasons examined the performance of *Sesbania rostrata*, *S. aculeata*, *S. speciosa*, and *Crotalaria juncea* L.

The 1986 wet season crop was sown 13 May at 30- × 10-cm spacing in 8- ×

2-m plots. This experiment was a single unreplicated plot. The 1986-87 dry season crop was broadcast on 12 Dec in 25- × 4-m plots. The 1987 wet season crop was sown on 6 Jun at 30-cm spacing for *Sesbania* species and 20-cm spacing for *C. juncea* in 25- × 5-m plots. The Dec and Jun experiments were laid

out in a randomized block design with three replications. Fertilizer was 20 kg N and 17.6 kg P/ha, incorporated before sowing. One irrigation was given at sowing for germination.

Plant stands were uniform in all plots. Growth was recorded on 10 plants collected at random at 48 d after sowing

Table 1. Plant height and fresh weight of green manure crops sown in May 1986 in Hyderabad, India.

Green manure crop	Plant height (cm)	Fresh weight (g)
<i>S. aculeata</i>	151.5	172.0
<i>S. rostrata</i>	158.0	158.0
<i>S. speciosa</i>	77.6	69.6

Table 2. Plant height and fresh and dry weight of green manure crops grown in dry (Dec) and wet (Jun) seasons. Hyderabad, India, 1986-87.

Green manure	Plant height (cm)			Fresh weight (g)			Dry weight (g)		
	Dry season 1986	Wet season 1987	Mean	Dry season 1986	Wet season 1987	Mean	Dry season 1986	Wet season 1987	Mean
<i>S. aculeata</i>	38.3	148.0	93.2	10.7	57.3	34.0	2.7	14.0	9.4
<i>S. rostrata</i>	25.3	139.0	82.2	9.4	58.0	33.7	2.4	13.7	9.0
<i>C. juncea</i> L.	29.0	84.0	56.5	6.0	24.3	15.2	1.7	6.0	3.8
Mean	30.9	123.7		8.7	46.6		2.3	11.2	
LSD (0.05)									
Season		9.7		5.0			0.8		
Green manure		11.9		6.1			1.0		
Season × green manure		16.8		8.7			1.4		
CV (%)		12.0		17.2			11.8		

(DAS) for May and Dec sown crops and at 57 DAS for the Jun crop.

S. aculeata and *S. rostrum* had similar performance irrespective of date of sowing (Table 1, 2). The May-sown crop performed best (May is the most appropriate time for growing a green manure crop to fit local rice-based cropping systems). The Jun-sown crop had reduced plant height and less biomass production. The Dec crops had very poor growth. □

Biofertilizer efficiency in lowland rice

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We studied the efficiency of blue-green algae, Azospirillum, and azolla alone and with 50, 75, and 100 kg N/ha during wet and dry seasons 1986-87. Treatments were in a randomized block design with three replications.

Azospirillum lipoferum at 10^8 cells/g inoculant was inoculated at 1 kg/ha by seedling root dip for 20 min. A composite culture of blue-green algae was applied in the soil at 10 kg/ha 10 d after transplanting (DT). *Azolla pinnata* was established as dual crop at 1 t/ha 10 DT and the azolla mat incorporated at 20 d and 40 d.

Effect of biofertilizers on grain yield. Madurai, India, 1986-87.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Kharif (CO 37)	Rabi (IR20)
100 kg N/ha alone	5.9	4.2
75 kg N/ha alone	5.7	6.0
50 kg N/ha alone	5.0	3.8
75 kg N/ha + blue-green algae	6.2	4.5
75 kg N/ha + azolla	5.9	4.5
75 kg N/ha + Azospirillum	6.4	4.5
50 kg N/ha + blue-green algae	5.6	4.0
50 kg N/ha + azolla	5.2	4.1
50 kg N/ha + Azospirillum	5.9	4.0
Blue-green algae alone	4.8	3.2
Azolla alone	4.6	3.3
Azospirillum alone	4.9	3.3
No fertilizer control	4.1	2.8
LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.3

Azospirillum with 75 kg N/ha influenced grain yield the most, with a significant increase in wet season rice and a dry season yield comparable to that with 100 kg N/ha (see table). In

both seasons, yields with blue-green algae and 75 kg N/ha or dual cropping of azolla, and that with Azospirillum with 50 kg N/ha were comparable with yield with 100 kg N/ha. □

Effect of Azospirillum biofertilizer on rice yield

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We compared the effect of Azospirillum biofertilizer with that of organic manure

at various levels of N during kharif (Jun-Sep) and rabi (Oct-Feb) 1986-87. Test varieties were IR50 in kharif and IR20 in rabi. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications.

Soil was a sandy loam with pH 6.8, EC 0.43 dS/m, and 297-40-153 kg available NPK/ha. Farmyard manure

Table 1. Productive tillers and grain yield with organic manure and Azospirillum application at 4 N levels.^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1986 kharif.

Treatment	Productive tillers (no./m ²)					Grain yield (t/ha)				
	No N	49 kg N/ha	73 kg N/ha	98 kg N/ha	Mean	No N	49 kg N/ha	73 kg N/ha	98 kg N/ha	Mean
Control	487	531	549	566	533	3.2	3.8	3.9	4.1	3.8
5 t FYM/ha	501	544	556	572	543	3.3	3.7	4.0	4.4	3.9
Azospirillum (nursery + main field)	535	550	556	564	551	3.3	3.9	4.1	4.2	3.8
FYM + Azospirillum	489	521	550	576	534	3.2	3.8	4.1	4.5	3.9
Mean	503	536	553	569		3.3	3.8	4.0	4.3	
						LSD		LSD		
						FYM × Azospirillum		ns		
						Levels of N		0.2		
						FYM × Azospirillum × N level		ns		

^aN applied per soil test recommendation, with 98 kg N/ha = 100% N.

Table 2. Productive tillers and grain yield as influenced by organic manure and Azospirillum at 4 N levels.^a Tamil Nadu, 1986 rabi.

Treatment	Productive tillers (no./m ²)					Grain yield (t/ha)				
	No N	49 kg N/ha	73 kg N/ha	98 kg N/ha	Mean	No N	49 kg N/ha	73 kg N/ha	98 kg N/ha	Mean
Control	334	357	378	406	369	2.9	3.6	3.9	4.1	3.6
5 t FYM/ha	335	367	373	385	365	2.7	3.7	4.1	3.9	3.6
Azospirillum (seed + nursery + root dip + main field)	351	370	364	453	385	3.1	4.0	4.0	4.4	3.9
FYM + Azospirillum	380	367	392	454	398	3.0	3.8	4.0	4.6	3.9
Mean	350	365	377	425		2.9	3.8	4.0	4.3	
						LSD		LSD		
						FYM × Azospirillum		21		
						Levels of N		16		
						FYM × Azospirillum × N level		32		

^aN applied per soil test recommendation, with 98 kg N/ha = 100% N.